

MODELLING DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT PANELS UNDER TYRE RUBBER IMPACT

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SUMMARY

The paper uses meso-scale composites ply damage models with an energy based delamination failure criteria in an explicit FE code to study damage progression in composite panels under impact. A study is made of damage in frame stiffened aircraft panels and a composite wing lower cover panel impacted by tyre fragments.

KEYWORDS: *Composite damage, delamination models, FE code developments, stiffened aircraft panels, simulation of impact damage*

INTRODUCTION

A critical safety issue for the design of primary aircraft structures is vulnerability and damage tolerance due to foreign object impacts from bird strike, hail, tyre rubber and metal fragments. New composite aircraft structures are particularly vulnerable to impact damage, due to the thin composite skins and the generally brittle behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resins. Physical phenomena associated with impact damage and progressive collapse of composite structures are complex, and predictive models and simulation tools for design and analysis are being widely investigated. The paper uses meso-scale composites damage models [1], [2] in explicit FE codes to study damage progression in composite structures under impact. Key issues discussed in [3] are the development of models for composites in-ply damage and delamination failure, modelling bonded and riveted joints, materials laws for soft body impactors such as birds and tyre rubber, and the efficient implementation of the materials models into FE codes. Multi-scale modelling techniques are required because impact damage is localised and requires fine scale modelling of delamination and ply damage at the micromechanics level, whilst the structural length scales are much larger.

Materials parameters for the meso-scale ply damage models have been obtained from extensive test programmes at the DLR and by external partners on UD carbon/epoxy materials, including monotonic and cyclic tests in tension, shear and compression, from which ply damage parameters and delamination failure energies G_{IC} and G_{IIC} have been determined. Numerical studies have been carried out mainly at small specimen and idealised structure level [3] to validate the meso-scale models, and analysis of delamination tests helped identify critical parameters for the cohesive interface model. Gas gun impact tests on composite structures at the DLR have shown the critical influence of delamination failures in controlling local energy absorption and impact penetration for both hard and soft body impactors. In the case of tyre rubber impacts on composite structures observed damage is usually dominated by delamination rather than

fibre fracture. Since delamination is a through-thickness failure mode current modelling is frequently based on solid elements at the composite ply level connected by cohesive interfaces, as reviewed by Hallett [4]. These techniques are now well established and are being applied at the specimen level or for structural details, such as delamination at free edges. However, the fine scale 3D FE meshes required are not yet appropriate for modelling delamination damage in aircraft structures due to the large size of the FE models and high computer costs. Thus in the current work, as discussed by the authors in [5], FE panel models suitable for application to impact failure in aircraft structures were developed based on stacked shell elements for the composite laminate connected through cohesive interfaces. This can be described as a 2.5D FE model, where the stacked shell technique allows a composite laminate to split into plies or sublaminates when the cohesive interface fails and delamination occurs. Focus in this paper is the application of the modelling techniques to predict damage progression in frame stiffened composite panels due to impact from tyre rubber fragments, followed by study of impact damage in a wing lower cover.

MESO-SCALE PLY DAMAGE MODEL

In the meso-scale composite models the laminate is modelled by layered shell elements or stacked shells with cohesive interfaces which may fail by delamination. The shells are composed of composite plies which behave as homogeneous orthotropic elastic or elastic-plastic damaging materials whose properties are degraded on loading by microcracking prior to ultimate failure. A CDM formulation is used in which ply degradation parameters are internal state variables which are governed by damage evolution equations. For shell elements a plane stress formulation with orthotropic symmetry axes (x_1, x_2) is required. The in-plane stress and strain components are

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12})^T \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e = (\varepsilon_{11}^e, \varepsilon_{22}^e, 2\varepsilon_{12}^e)^T. \quad (1)$$

Constitutive laws for orthotropic elastic materials with internal damage parameters are described in [1] - [3], and take the general form

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e = \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ are vectors of stress and elastic strain, and \mathbf{S} is the elastic compliance matrix. Using a strain equivalent damage mechanics formulation, the elastic compliance matrix \mathbf{S} may then be written:

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/E_1(1-d_1) & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 1/E_2(1-d_2) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12}(1-d_{12}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where E_1, E_2 are the initial (undamaged) Young's moduli in the fibre and transverse fibre directions, and G_{12} is the (undamaged) in-plane shear modulus. The principal Poisson's ratio ν_{12} is assumed here not to be independently degraded. The ply model introduces three scalar damage parameters d_1, d_2, d_{12} which have values $0 \leq d_i < 1$ and represent modulus reductions under different loading conditions due to micro-damage in the material. For UD plies d_1 controls damage in the fibre direction, d_2 damage transverse to the fibres and d_{12} controls in-plane shear failure. For fabric plies d_1 and d_2 are associated with damage or failure in the principal fibre directions.

In the general formulation [1] damage energy release rates Y_1 , Y_2 , Y_{12} or 'conjugate forces' are introduced corresponding to 'driving' mechanisms for materials damage.

$$Y_1 = \sigma_{11}^2 / (2E_1(1-d_1)^2), \quad Y_2 = \sigma_{22}^2 / (2E_2(1-d_2)^2), \quad Y_{12} = \sigma_{12}^2 / (2G_{12}(1-d_{12})^2) \quad (4)$$

The ply model is completed by assuming damage evolution equations in which the three ply damage parameters d_1 , d_2 , d_{12} are functions of Y_1 , Y_2 , Y_{12} . Specific forms for these functions are postulated based on study of ply specimen test data. The formulation of the damage evolution equations in the Ladevèze CDM models is physically based and allows generalisations to include features such as shear plasticity and rate dependence. Test data on unidirectional (UD) carbon fibre reinforced epoxy presented in [1] show that damage evolution equations for the transverse and shear damage d_2 , d_{12} are coupled through a linear dependence on $\sqrt{Y_2}$ and $\sqrt{Y_{12}}$. Test data on carbon and glass fabric/epoxy materials [3] lead to damage evolution equations in which fibre tension/compression damage parameters d_1 , d_2 are elastic damaging and linear in $\sqrt{Y_1}$ and $\sqrt{Y_2}$ respectively, but decoupled from elastic-plastic ply shear damage in which d_{12} is a nonlinear function of $\sqrt{Y_{12}}$.

For in-plane shear, ply deformations are controlled by matrix behaviour which may be inelastic, or irreversible, due to the presence of extensive matrix cracking or plasticity. On unloading this can lead to permanent deformations in the ply. The extension of the meso-scale model to include these irreversible damage effects is based on the assumption that the total strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is written as the sum of elastic $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and plastic strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$ ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$). The elastic strain components are given by the ply elastic-damage model defined in (2) and (3) with appropriate damage evolution functions. The plastic strains are associated with the matrix dominated in-plane shear and transverse behaviour in UD plies. A classical plasticity model is used with an elastic domain function and hardening law applied to the 'effective' stresses in the damaged material. Cyclic loading tests are performed in which both the elastic and irreversible plastic strains are measured where the accumulated effective plastic strain p is determined over the complete loading cycle. The model is completed by specifying the plastic hardening function $R(p)$. A typical form which models test data fairly well is an index function, which leads here to the general equation:

$$R(p) = \beta p^m \quad (5)$$

so that the ply plasticity model for fabric plies depends on the parameters β , the power index m and the yield stress R_o . For UD plies there is an additional shear/transverse damage coupling parameter to determine.

Ultimate ply failure is controlled by setting the damage parameters $d_i = 1$, at threshold energy values Y_{1f} , Y_{2f} , Y_{12f} . From the definitions for the Y_i in (4) these ultimate failure conditions may be simply related to ply failure stresses or strains. Additionally the model allows well-known multiaxial ply failure criteria such as maximum strain, modified Puck, etc to be applied. In this case the CDM model is used to describe ply degradation such as matrix cracking, whilst ply ultimate failure may be controlled by fibre fracture. This is achieved by setting all the d_i equal to 1 when the multiaxial failure envelope is reached. Further details of the ply damage and plasticity model, the tests required to determine the required parameters, and the failure models are given in [1] and [3].

DELAMINATION MODELLING: COHESIVE INTERFACE MODEL

Delamination failures occur in composite structures due to local contact forces in critical regions of load introduction and at free edges. They are caused by the low, resin dominated, through-thickness shear and tensile properties found in laminated structures. Because delamination failure causes rapid interface crack propagation, failure models are generally based on fracture mechanics ideas rather than conventional stress based failure models. A general framework for composites delamination models is described in [2], in which the thin solid interface is modelled as a sheet of zero thickness across which there is continuity of surface tractions but jumps in displacements. General interface constitutive laws are then presented within a CDM formulation. The approach used here follows more closely [6] where specific forms of the interface stress-displacement laws are assumed. The equations of the model are given here for the case of mode I tensile failure at an interface. The terminology of the previous section is used in which (x_1, x_2) is in the laminate plane and x_3 is the coordinate through the thickness of the thin laminate. Let σ_{33} be the tensile stress applied at the interface, u_3 the displacement jump across the interface, and k_3 the interface tensile stiffness. An elastic damaging interface stress-displacement model is assumed:

$$\sigma_{33} = k_3(1 - d_3) u_3 \quad (6)$$

with through-thickness tensile damage parameter d_3 , $0 \leq d_3 \leq 1$. The damage evolution equation is assumed to have the particular form

$$d_3 = 0, \quad 0 \leq u_3 < u_{30},$$

$$d_3 = c_1(1 - u_{30}/u_3), \quad u_{30} \leq u_3 \leq u_{3m}, \quad \text{with} \quad c_1 = u_{3m}/(u_{3m} - u_{30}) \quad (7)$$

It can be verified that with this particular choice of damage function d_3 , the stress-displacement function has the triangular form shown in Fig. 1, and u_{30} , u_{3m} correspond to the displacement at the peak stress σ_{33m} and at ultimate failure respectively. The tensile failure model requires the two constants u_{30} , u_{3m} . Furthermore these damage evolution constants may be defined in terms of σ_{33m} and G_{IC} , the critical fracture energy under mode I interface fracture, by:

$$u_{30} = \sigma_{33m} / k_3 \quad u_{3m} = 2G_{IC} / \sigma_{33m}. \quad (8)$$

In this case from these expressions it can be shown that the area under the curve in Fig. 1 is equal to the fracture energy G_{IC} . This interface model therefore represents an initially elastic interface, which is progressively degraded after reaching a maximum tensile failure stress σ_{33m} so that the mode I fracture energy is fully absorbed at separation.

For mode I interply failure the interface energy G_I at displacement u_3 is defined as

$$G_I = \int_0^{u_3} \sigma_{33} du_3 \quad (9)$$

When G_I exceeds the critical fracture energy value G_{IC} , then the mode I fracture energy is absorbed and the delamination crack is advanced. These equations may be used to define conditions for interface elements in an implicit code as in [4], [6] or applied to a cohesive interface contact law in an explicit FE code as described in [5], [7].

Figure 1: Idealised mode I interface stress-displacement function $\sigma_{33} - u_3$

For mode II interface shear fracture a similar damage interface law to (6) is assumed, with equivalent set of damage constants u_{130} , u_{13m} and critical shear mode II fracture energy G_{IIc} . In general loading of an interface there will be some form of mixed mode delamination failure involving both shear and tensile failure. This is incorporated in the model by assuming a mixed mode failure condition, which for mode I/mode II coupling could be represented by an interface failure envelope such as that generally assumed [6], [7]:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^n + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}}\right)^n = e_D \leq 1 \quad (10)$$

Here G_I and G_{II} are the monitored interface strain energies in modes 1 and 2 respectively, G_{IC} and G_{IIc} are the corresponding critical fracture energies and the constant n is chosen to fit the mixed mode fracture test data. Typically n is found to be between 1 and 2. Failure at the interface is imposed by degrading stresses when $e_D < 1$ using (6), (7) and the corresponding shear relation. When $e_D \geq 1$ there is delamination and the interface separates. Experimental testing work has been undertaken, using a mixed mode fracture test, which indicates that the interaction of energies is approximately linear in typical composite materials [7]. Thus the interface traction failure law for typical composites could be based on (10) with $n = 1$ for mixed mode loading.

TYRE RUBBER IMPACT ON COMPOSITE PANEL STRUCTURES

The ply damage and failure models discussed in the previous sections were implemented in the commercial explicit crash and impact code PAM-CRASHTM in collaboration with the software company Engineering Systems International [8], [9]. The code uses a bilinear 4-node quadrilateral isoparametric shell element due to Belytschko with uniform reduced integration in bending and shear. A Mindlin-Reissner shell formulation is used with a layered shell description to model a composite ply, a sublaminar or the complete laminate, depending on the detail required. The layered shells contain one integration point per ply, so that at least 4 plies are required in a layered shell for the correct bending stiffness. For the delamination model the composite laminate is treated as a stack of shell elements. Each ply or sublaminar ply group is represented by layered shell elements and the individual sublaminar shells are connected together using cohesive interfaces with the interface traction-displacement law. Interface contact may be broken when the interface energy dissipated reaches the mixed mode delamination energy criteria (10). This 2.5D FE model for composite laminates, the 'stacked shell' approach, is an efficient way of modelling delamination,

with the advantage that the critical integration time step is relatively large since it depends on the area size of the shell elements not on the inter-ply thickness, see [7] for further details and validation studies.

Modelling impact in stiffened composite panels

To demonstrate the application of the composites damage models and stacked shell modelling strategy, a study was made within the EU ALCAS project [10] of tyre rubber fragments impacting aircraft composite panels with bonded and riveted C-frames. Fig. 2 shows the geometry of the stiffened panel and rectangular rubber fragment impactor. FE analyses were made to predict impact damage for tyre rubber fragment mass 0.85 kg impacting at a velocity of 93 m/s with impact angle 70° , which represents the typical impact scenario of a burst tyre fragment on a lower fuselage panel during start or landing. The panel structure is composed of a 1690 x 1000 mm composite panel stiffened by six C-frames, 1300 mm in length, 120 mm in height, flange width 41 mm, which are bonded and connected by riveted fasteners to the panel, with frame spacing 330 mm. For the impact analysis, the panel is assumed to be clamped at the edges of the long sides and at the ends of the C-frames.

Figure 2: Overview of the model and orientation of the rubber fragment at impact

The main panel is composed of 22 UD carbon/epoxy plies with a quasi-isotropic layup and thickness about 6.0 mm. A stacked shell laminate model was used and after preliminary studies with different configurations, the laminate was idealised by four sub-laminates of layered shells connected by three cohesive interfaces. This approximation limits the role of delamination damage to three interfaces, but keeps the model size within bounds. The C-frames consisted of 15 plies giving 4.1 mm thickness and were modelled as single layered composite shells. The bonding of the C-frames to the skin was modelled by a cohesive interface, to allow possible debonding. The riveted fasteners are modelled using mesh independent link elements, with all degrees of freedom are tied, which fail at given tensile and shear loads. The final structure model consists of 130,450 shells with a typical element edge length of 8 mm. Materials parameters for the meso-scale ply models were obtained from an extensive test programme carried out in the ALCAS project, including monotonic and cyclic tests in tension and compression for determining ply damage parameters and fracture toughness tests for delamination failure energies G_{IC} and G_{IIC} .

The tyre rubber projectile represents tyre tread, without fibre reinforcements, and was ca. 210 x 210 x 16.5 mm in size, with slight curvature and mass 0.85 kg. Rubber may be

modelled using a hyperelastic Mooney-Rivlin material model, as discussed in [11], [12]. A large strain tensile test programme was carried out at the DLR to determine the Mooney-Rivlin parameters of aircraft tyre rubber and the model was verified for tensile strains up to about 50%. The rubber projectile was modeled by solid elements, with mesh size ca. 2.7 mm, giving 35,500 elements.

a) Upper face ply damage b) Degradation in upper delamination interface

Fig.2: Predicted damage in panel under rubber impact (0.85 kg, 93 m/s, $\alpha = \beta = 70^\circ$)

Impact simulations were performed with the commercial explicit code PAM-CRASH [9]. Typical numerical results are shown in Fig. 2 for the case of tyre rubber fragment with orientation angles defined in Fig. 1, $\alpha = \beta = 70^\circ$. The angle α determines the impact angle to the panel face, whilst β controls the orientation of the projectile to the flight direction. The impact point is chosen midway between two C-frames which is considered to be the worst case for impact damage in this structure. With such deformable projectiles skin penetration is not usually important and simulations show that the rubber projectile rebounds causing ply damage without fracture in the contact zone and delamination damage over a wider region due to wave effects. Fig. 2a shows ply damage contours in the upper sub-laminate and Fig. 2b delamination at the upper cohesive interface. Ply damage propagates beyond the impact point to the adjacent C-frame interfaces. In Fig. 2b, the white regions represent delamination failures which extend to the bay panel between frames. The failure of the adhesive bond between the C-frame ahead of the impact point and the skin is also predicted, whereas the fasteners do not fail and keep the C-frame attached to the skin. Tyre rubber impact tests on the panels have since been carried out within the ALCAS project and the simulation results here are in good qualitative agreement with damage observed for similar impact test conditions. More detailed results of parameter studies with this model, in which a comparison is made of two different carbon composite materials in the structure, can be found in [13].

Impact damage in aircraft wing panel

The methodology developed above is now being applied to a composite lateral wing lower cover panel for a transport aircraft which is also subjected to tyre fragment impacts. The lateral wing structure has length ca 11 m, with a span at the widest point of 4 m, and 12 lateral ribs. The lower cover is manufactured as a single composite shell, reinforced longitudinally with T-stringers and near to its centre line has a row of non-structural fuel tank access cover (FTAC) panels. In the critical region above the landing gear the lower cover panel is vulnerable to burst tyre fragment impacts and this impact

scenario is relevant for wing certification. As discussed above fine scale FE models are required to predict localised impact damage in composite panel structures, so this represents a significant multiscale problem for the aircraft designer. The work presented here develops a detailed FE model of the impacted region using the 2.5D stacked shell approach to study local damage as a function of the impact conditions. In future work, this model could be linked through a suitable interface to larger scale FE models of the full lower cover structure and domain decomposition methods used for the analysis.

Fig. 3: Wing bay panel FE model with FTAC (half model)

As a representative substructure the wing cover panel in a bay between two ribs was selected, at the inner part of the lateral wing above the landing gear, where impacts from burst tyre fragments could take place. At this point the lateral wing is about 4 m wide with about 8 stringers across the width. It was decided that the critical impact case is a rubber projectile in the bay near the FTAC, since damage to this cover panel could lead to fuel leakage from the wing tanks. Fig. 3 shows the FE model of the representative composite panel chosen between adjacent wing ribs and main stringers. The panel is a composite laminate 1600 x 800 mm in size and 24 mm thick, with two T-stringers between which, for the computations presented here, there is an aluminium FTAC. This is ribbed and has a sealed, flanged interface to the lower cover panel. Fig. 3 shows the half model of the structure from the inside, with the rubber projectile impacting from below at a point between stringer and FTAC. The edges of the panel element were assumed to be clamped, this represents attachments to the very stiff wing ribs on the long sides perpendicular to the T-stringers and the constraint of the adjacent T-stringers preventing lateral displacement at the short sides.

The cover laminate is fabricated from UD carbon/epoxy plies with an assumed quasi-isotropic layup in the model here. Experience with the rubber impact on CFRP panels described above suggests again that delamination damage will be important. Thus the 24 mm thick laminate was modelled by 12 stacked shells with 11 cohesive interfaces, so that delamination failures could be studied. The composite T-stringers are 5 mm thick, 60 mm in height, with 88 mm wide flanges and are attached to the cover panel by a cohesive interface to represent the bond. The composites plies were modelled by the meso-scale damage model described above. Ply and delamination data measured at the DLR and representative of the carbon/epoxy material used in the ALCAS wings were used for the analyses. The ribbed FTAC was modelled in shell elements with an elastic-plastic materials model assumed for aluminium. The FTAC panel is attached to the

cover by 40 bolted connections around its circumference, which were modelled by riveted link elements with failure. The composite panel structure and FTAC required about 140,000 shell elements.

For the results presented here the rubber tyre fragment projectile was rectangular with dimensions 440 x 250 x 14 mm, mass 1.6 kg and impact velocity 80 m/s with impact angle 45° to the panel lower face. The impact conditions chosen represent a tyre fragment with approximately 1% of the aircraft tyre mass with impact velocities representative of start or landing. For this load case the tyre fragment contained fabric reinforcements over 5 mm of its thickness. These are considerably stiffer than the tread rubber [12] and a projectile model was developed composed of solid rubber elements, with the Mooney-Rivlin material model discussed above, coupled to reinforcing fabric plies of orthotropic elastic shell elements whose properties were measured in a test programme at the DLR. The rubber fragment model consisted of about 12,500 solids and shells.

FE simulation with PAM-CRASH [9] of impact from the 1.6 kg tyre rubber fragment at 80 m/s and 45° impact angle showed rebound of the rubber projectile, accompanied by panel bending at the impact position which caused some small plastic deformation at the FTAC inner flange, but no serious damage to the access panel bolts or its interface to the lower cover. Fig. 4a shows ply damage contours at the inside of the lower cover and Fig. 4b shows a plan view of delamination damage at the impact point, which is localised to the stringer-panel flange interface. No fibre fracture in the lower cover was predicted. Impact tests on real aircraft wing structures needed for validation of these models are not available and would be very costly to generate. Such tests would usually only be used to support certification once the design is finalised. Validation studies on idealised structures suggest, however, that this idealised multiscale strategy with stacked shells looks promising for damage predictions in larger aircraft structures. The model is now being used for parameter studies and by increasing impact energy and changing the contact point it is possible to study the threshold at which the cover panel, the FTAC or its sealing could be damaged. These studies are ongoing and should provide information to assist in the design of damage tolerant composite wing structures.

a) Ply damage in lower cover

b) Delamination damage at outer surface

Fig.4: Predicted damage in lower cover bay panel under tyre impact (1.6 kg, 80 m/s, 45° angle)

CONCLUSIONS

The paper presented a materials failure model for UD composites laminates including both interply delamination and intraply damage which has been implemented as a 2.5D FE model with stacked shells and cohesive interfaces in the dynamic FE code PAM-CRASH. Additional FE models suitable for modelling large deformations in rubber and reinforced rubber were also developed for the tyre fragment projectiles. The modelling techniques were successfully applied to the impact simulation of tyre rubber fragments on carbon/epoxy aircraft panels stiffened with C-frames. In all cases, the projectile rebounded and caused some local damage. Observed damage such as delamination or frame debonding may be away from the impact position due to wave effects. For the load cases studied, full separation of the frames near the impact position was not observed as the riveted connections remained intact. A second study was made on a composite wing lower cover panel also subjected to tyre rubber impact. The critical aspect of the design is to ensure that the fuel tank access cover (FTAC) and the sealing to the lower cover do not fracture, which was shown to be the case for the impact condition analysed here. In both simulation studies the impact kinetic energies were high, in the range 5.12 – 7.35 kJ. However, for rubber projectiles a large part of this impact energy is stored as elastic strain energy in the rubber due to the large deformations, which reduces damage in the composite structures. The work emphasises the importance of efficient delamination models for soft body impact damage in composite structures. This is traditionally modelled with fine scale solid elements at the ply level and cohesive interfaces. Such 3D models are less appropriate for predicting damage in larger aircraft structures and it was shown that reasonably good results may be obtained with the 2.5D models without excessive computing costs. The work demonstrates the importance of multiscale computational strategies if impact damage is to be simulated in larger aircraft structures.

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